

Data management plan for development and piloting of meta-cognitive interventions for reducing engagement with misinformation

Version 2

Description

The goal of the project is to develop quick and easy-to-implement interventions that would help information users to recognize misinformation and reduce the motivation to engage in the further dissemination of misinformation. By expanding the existing knowledge base on the cognitive processes of online information processing and the effectiveness of meta-cognitive interventions, it is planned to create a set of interventions that can be used both in active training of information users and also integrated into existing technical solutions for online information use (e.g. as plugins for Internet browsers or mobile app add-ons). The main focus of the project is on increasing the ability of users to recognise errors and biases in their reasoning process, evaluating information in different contexts, but especially evaluating information consistent with their beliefs, attitudes and values. Data collected during the project includes survey data and behavioral and attitude measurements during computerised experiments.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Development and piloting of meta-cognitive interventions for reducing engagement with misinformation (Izp-2024/1-0176)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data management plan for development and piloting of meta-cognitive interventions for reducing engagement with misinformation](#)

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Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Development and piloting of meta-cognitive interventions for reducing engagement with misinformation \(lzp-2024/1-0176\)](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Survey data of Latvian Internet users

A diverse sample (N = 400) of Internet users from Latvia has been surveyed by a market research company Solid Data. The data file contains information about the respondents habits of social network usage, self-rated evaluation of information on social networks, as well as beliefs in propaganda messages related to the most common topics of misinformation.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data set provides general information about the self-reported social network usage habits, information processing habits and disinformation-related attitudes of Latvian Internet users. This information is used as the basis for planning experiments and other experiments within the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV

- SAV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No existing data usable for this purpose is available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Social science researchers in psychology, sociology, communication science, political science, as well as computer science researchers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Document Description -- Title, principal investigator, geography of the dataset

Study Description -- description of the study at a broad level, including information on geographic and temporal scope as well as methodological information.

Files Description -- description of the physical data file(s) in terms of record and variable counts, logical record length, etc.

Data (Variables) Description -- detailed information on each data item, including question text, variable label, category labels and values, etc.

Survey questionnaire file

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

zenodo.org

Recommended by the implementing institution and the funder of the project

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS, JASP, R, RStudio, Python, any other data analysis software that allows importing .csv or .sav format files

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

.csv is open, non-proprietary data format. .sav is proprietary SPSS data format, but importable to multiple open-source data analysis applications (e.g., R, RStudio, JASP, Python).

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Recommended by the implementing institution and the funder of the project

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-03-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

There will be no limits on the re-use period.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project financing

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Girts Dimdins (0000-0002-4129-1743)

The project head is responsible for data management during the project and keeping the data up to date after the publication and after the closure of the project.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The data will be kept in the public repository and kept up-to-date after the project conclusion.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- IRB protocol
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

All data security measures will be implemented in line with the institutional policies defined by the University of Latvia (project implementer). In line with these policies, the data are stored in a designated project folder on LU Sharepoint server, accessible only to the members of the project group.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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